

Evaluating Tanzania's Potential in Establishing a Food Additive Industry in the Country: A Study of the Production of Food Texturizing Agents

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Abstract:

The paper investigated the availability of resources in Tanzania with regards to the production of food additives. The focus is on the resources needed and the technologies utilised. The study focused on a specific class of additives, texturizing agents, and looked at different agro-based sources including seeds, plants, agro-processing by-products and agro-waste that can be utilised. These sources were linked to the industrial processing technologies and assessed for adaptability in the country. The aim of the study is to theoretically assess the potential of producing additives with resources available in the country. The study was online-based research utilising secondary data to understand the situation at hand. Results indicated that there is an untapped potential in the country with regards to the additives value chain. With proper support and under the national initiative to strive for industrialization, Tanzania can successfully develop additives and supply both domestic and regional markets.

Keywords: Agar, Guar, Xanthan, Starch, Processing aids.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Food additives are a part of food processing aids which “are any substance not normally consumed as a food by itself and not normally used as a typical ingredient of the food, whether or not it has nutritive value, the intentional addition of which to food for a technological (including organoleptic) purpose in the manufacture, processing, preparation, treatment, packing, packaging, transport or holding of such food results, or may be reasonably expected to result (directly or indirectly), in it or its by-products becoming a component of or otherwise affecting the characteristics of such foods. The term does not include contaminants or substances added to food for maintaining or improving nutritional qualities” (Codex Alimentarius, 1995).

From the adopted definition, food additives are used to improve the food being produced and are not considered as ingredients. However, in a bid to ensure food safety, there is a need to declare them in case of allergens and/or animal origins (Ukwo *et al.*, 2022; Redan 2020). Additives have different sources and according to their composition they can be classified as organic or inorganic, obtained from natural sources or chemically synthesised (Wu *et al.*, 2022; Carocho *et al.*, 2014; Branen *et al.*, 2001). Additives can be classed according to their functionality with regards to the food. Additives of significant interest are the texturizing agents.

Texturing agents include substances that modify the overall texture to mouthfeel of the food products (Faustino *et al.*, 2019; Saha *et al.*, 2010). Texture is defined as the mechanical, geometrical, and surface characteristics of a product that can be perceived through mechanical, tactile, and where applicable visual and auditory receptors (Aktar, 2015; Pascua *et al.*, 2013). Whether the food will be smooth, gritty, brittle, elastic, soft, chewy, crumbly, cohesive, moist, dry or tender will rely on the interactions of different ingredients throughout its manufacturing process. Texturing agents are added to enhance these properties that might have been lost during processing (Dar *et al.*, 2014).

The main categories of texturizing agents are stabilizers and emulsifiers. Emulsifiers ensure that flavour (and oils) are dispersed throughout a food product while stabilizers provide the desired texture by preventing evaporation and deterioration of the volatile flavour oils (Codex, 2021; Faustino *et al.*, 2019). Common examples of emulsifiers are fatty acid esters, lecithin, hydrocolloids and gum acacia. Thermodynamically unstable products that can become unstable during storage due to various physicochemical mechanisms such as agglomeration, phase separation and Ostwald ripening, are treated with emulsifiers to make them stable.

2. FOOD ADDITIVES AND PROCESSING INDUSTRIES

Stresses on the global food value chain due to climate change, economic and political upheaval have highlighted the vulnerabilities of the national food value chains especially in developing countries such as Tanzania (Singh *et al.*, 2023; Wheeler *et al.*, 2013;).

Processing industries in Tanzania, especially the small-scale food industries outline limited supply of raw material as a challenge (Mtenga and Ripanda, 2021; Sutton and Olomi, 2012). The increase in food processing industries amidst the drive for industrialization nationally, highlights the need to increase the domestic supply of raw materials.

While additives are minor portion of the process, the current food industries import large quantities to be able to produce their products (Export Genius, 2023). The presence of a domestic supply chain of additives will strengthen the food processing industries, essentially aiding them in reducing production costs and safeguarding the supply (Calignano and Mercurio, 2023). The global food additive market was worth \$114.35 billion in 2023 and is projected to grow by at least 5% (Grand View Research, 2023). Investment in this market through established production plants is potential income generation for the nation.

3. THE STUDY

Tanzanian food industries especially the larger scale industries import food additives. The study looked at food additives, specifically those under texturizing functional class to determine the potential of establishing additive processing industries in the country in terms of available raw materials and technology. The study focused on four examples of texturizing agents (Text box 1) to guide the research. The research question was “Does Tanzania have the resources necessary to successfully establish a food additives industry?”

The study was an online based study, utilising the internet to access information and obtain the necessary data to answer the research question. A qualitative based investigation, data was collected through internet searches (Google and Google Scholar) to ensure inclusion of both peer-reviewed and grey literature. The data collection was conducted between April 2024-August 2024.

Due to the expansive nature of the texturizing functional class, four well known additives of this group were selected as the focus of the study; Agar (E406), Guar gum (E412), Xanthan gum (E415) and Modified starch (E1412/E1422/1414) due to their potential production utilising plant related sources.

The data collection was guided using the template below:

Name of Additive	
Characteristics of the additive	
Food applications	
Production process	
Organic sources	
Availability of source/Technology	

3.1 Findings

The selected texturizing agents (Xanthan, guar, agar and starch) guided the assessment with a focus on raw material sources, technological requirements and policies and regulations. Text Box 1 and Table 1 introduces these agents and their applications in food industry.

Text Box 1: SELECTED TEXTURIZING AGENTS

Xanthan (E415)

Xanthan gum is an extracellular polysaccharide, best known as an emulsifier, a stabilizer and thickener. Xanthan gum is not found in nature, nor is it extracted from an organic source, rather it is manufactured by taking a carbohydrate and fermenting it with a bacterium. *Xanthomonas spp.* are gram negative plant-pathogenic bacteria, that ferments sugar such as glucose or fructose and creates a broth that when treated with alcohol becomes solid and upon drying turns into a fine white powder or granules. The characteristics of Xanthan gum include high solubility, highly viscous, exhibits pseudoplasticity and thermostability while resistance to pH changes. Additionally, the substance has a low calorific nature (Revin *et al.*, 2023; Gbadamosi *et al.*, 2022; Lopes *et al.*, 2015). As a fine white powder, Xanthan gum is also tasteless and has been assessed with regards to safety when consumed.

Agar (E406)

Agar is a hydrophilic colloid extracted from seaweeds of the Rhodophyceae class where it is formed as part of their cell wall (Park *et al.*, 2020). Agar is isolated from the algae as an amorphous and translucent product sold as powder, flakes, or bricks (Dhingra *et al.*, 2021). A key characteristic of agar is its ability to form water soluble, transparent and thermos-reversible gels (Ayyakkalai *et al.*, 2024) make it an ideal component in different industries from food to laboratory applications. Other characteristics include the fact that it has a firm texture, can withstand high temperatures and has reversibility properties (Onyeaka & Nwabor, 2022).

Guar (E412)

Guar gum also called guaran, is a novel agrochemical processed from endosperm of cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) (Mudling *et al.*, 2014). These seeds are processed into guar gum powder, which is widely used across industries. The main properties of Guar Gum include solubility in water, flocculation properties, high viscosity across a broad range of pH among others (Morris, 2010). The gum is obtained through a mechanical process involving roasting, differential attrition, sieving, and polishing.

Starch (E1412/E1422/1414)

Starch is a natural biopolymer synthesized and stored in vegetables as an energy source. Native starch acts as a texturizing agent, acting as a thickener, stabilizer, and water retention agent (Singh *et al.*, 2007). However, composition of native starch makes it less than ideal for industrial use as the high amylose content increases its susceptibility to retrogradation as well as structural constraints that arise due to stresses such as extreme temperatures and pH (Ağagündüz *et al.*, 2023). Under these circumstances, native starch undergoes modification. Modified starch is defined as the resulting substances of edible starch that has undergone chemical treatments, physical or enzymatic treatment and may be acid or alkali thinned or beached (Phillips and Williams, 2009). The treatments make the starch less prone to breaking down or enhancing their effectiveness as stabilizers (Gibson *et al.*, 2018). Modified starch characteristics are dependent on the treatment applied. Starch has been shown to have different physicochemical and biological properties like higher solubility, reaction surface, absorptive capacity, and biological penetration rate (Wang *et al.*, 2020).

Table 1: Texturizing agents; application and functions

Application	Gel	Function	Reference
Bakery	Xanthan	Leavening agent, toughener, humectant stabilizer,	Murad <i>et al.</i> (2019); Sharma <i>et al.</i> (2006)
	Agar	Texturizer, humectant (moisture retaining) stabilizer,	Pandya <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Guar	Anti-caking agent, lubricant, binder, extender and stabilizer	Sumnu <i>et al.</i> (2010); Bogdanova <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Meat products	Guar	Binder, lubricant, stabilizer	Ercelebi and Ibanoglu (2010)
	Agar	Thickener, gelling agent, texturizer	Pandya <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Xanthan	Texturizer, humectant stabilizer,	Liao <i>et al.</i> (2020); Gao <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Beverages	Agar	Stabilizer	Ramadhan and Trilaksani (2017)
	Guar	Thickener, stabilizer	Herald <i>et al.</i> (2020)
	Xanthan	Thickener, emulsifier, stabilizer	Minocha and Garapat (2021)
Dairy products	Xanthan	Stabilizer, thickener, cryoprotectant (freezing stabilizer)	Asase <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	Guar	Stabilizer, emulsifier	Brennan and Tudorica (2008)
	Agar	Humectant	Tamime and Robinson (1985); Malaka <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Pet food	Xanthan	Homogenizer, stabilizer, binder	Suryawinshi <i>et al.</i> (2020); Sanches <i>et al.</i>

			(2014); Palanijar <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Syrups and toppings	Xanthan	Stabilizer, emulsifier, thickener, gelling agent	Sharma <i>et al.</i> (2006); Palanijar <i>et al.</i> (2011)
Sauces and gravies	Xanthan	Thickening agent	Palanijar <i>et al.</i> (2011); Paquet <i>et al.</i> (2014); Suryawinshi <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Analog rice	Agar	Binder,	Ashila and Rahmatunnisa (2021); Nateghi, <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Various food products (baked foods, confectionery, pasta, soups, sauces and mayonnaises)	Starch	Thickening, preservation and quality enhancer	Emeje and Blumenberg 2020

3.2 Technological requirements and raw materials

With the four agents, each has several different techniques used to produce them (see Table 2). However, the commonly used processes include fermentation, syneresis, pressure-based, and extraction-focused techniques. These processes and their conditions are outlined in the following sections. In combination with technology, production of additives rely on the availability of raw materials. The identified agents, except for Xanthan, are plant-based substances. However, Xanthan as well requires plants, as the microbe *Xanthomonas*, is isolated from different plants. This study therefore establishes the fact that required raw material may be a microbe derived from a plant, extracts from plants, parts of a plant and the by-product of a processed plant.

Table 2: Production techniques for the different food additives

Additive	Technique	References
Xanthan gum	Batch production	Habibi <i>et al.</i> (2017)
	Immobilized reactors for continuous process	Nejadmansouri <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Starch	Traditional: Dry and wet extraction	Dorantes-Fuertes <i>et al.</i> (2024)
	Chemical: Enzymatic extraction	Li <i>et al.</i> (2022); Sit <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	Improved: ozone, ultrasound, high-pressure processing, high homogenization processing, pulsed electric field, and cold plasma	Castro <i>et al.</i> (2015); Thirumdas <i>et al.</i> (2017); Mieles-Gomez <i>et al.</i> (2023); Minakawa <i>et al.</i> (2019); Kim <i>et al.</i> (2012)
Guar	Milling, pulverization and purification	Vishwakarma <i>et al.</i> (2016); Kurayadi <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Agar	Freeze-thaw method, syneresis	Pandya <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	Utilization of polyphosphates	Pandya <i>et al.</i> (2022); Matsushashi <i>et al.</i> (1971)
	applied pressure and alkali treatment of seaweed	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2023); Sousa <i>et al.</i> (2021)

Xanthan gum

Fermentation is the process utilised by industries to prepare Xanthan gum (Fig. 1). The process follows the batch (non-continuous) process under optimal conditions.

Currently, industrial production utilizes *X. campestris*. The genus *Xanthomonas*, is a genus of gram negative, aerobic and rod -shaped bacteria known for being a plant pathogen (Trudova, 2020). The genus has many known species, from which xanthan gum could be manufactured. Research has shown that these individual species and strains give xanthan gum of different rheological and physical properties. Rottave *et al.* (2009) and Gumus *et al.* (2010) conducted studies on different strains of *Xanthanomonas spp* indicating the yield of xanthan differs depending on the strain.

The relevant conditions for production include the presence of a carbon source, growth medium that consists of nitrogen, phosphate and magnesium sources, temperature conditions that range between 28 - 32 °C, pH 6.5-7.5 and oxygen supply within the range of 0.5l/min-15l/min. These factors are maintained in an aerobic environment with a strain *X. campestris* NRRL B-1459 being the selected organism used (Lopes *et al.*, 2015; Bhat *et al.*, 2022).

Once the process reaches completion, with the exhaustion of the substrate, the end-product is heat sterilized. Sterilization kills the *Xanthomonas* cells and deactivates enzymes capable of degrading plant polysaccharides. The process undergoes a cooling period, then precipitation is conducted with the aid of isopropanol. The final steps are filtrations and drying of the product (Lopes *et al.*, 2015).

To achieve optimal production, industrial plants must carefully evaluate bioreactor settings and select suitable operating system, whether batch or continuous to ensure the best configuration, the composition of the fermentation medium, and controlled production conditions of temperature, pH, agitation speed, aeration and fermentation time. All these factors result in a good yield of a gum with high quality, in the sense of suitable rheological properties and structure (Lopes *et al.*, 2015; Seviour *et al.*, 2011).

Research has investigated adaptations to the parameters necessary for xanthan gum production such as the effect of temperature variations on the yield. The best gum was obtained at the fermentation temperature of 28 °C (Da Silva *et al.*, 2018; Zakeri *et al.*, 2017). Higher temperatures than that yielded xanthan gum with low viscosity solutions due to low acetate and pyruvate and molecular weight, and vice versa for temperature around 24 °C (Lopes *et al.*, 2015; Bhat *et al.*, 2022). Care, therefore, must also be undertaken as the heat treatment has a degenerative effect on the polymer, even though

Figure 1: Industrial production process for xanthan gum (Source: Authors' own, based on Dey and Chatterji, 2023)

in some instances high viscosity was observed (Papagianni, *et al.*, 2001; Lopes *et al.*, 2015).

Due to the need for an aerobic environment, the speed at which the stirring is done affects the xanthan rheological complexity and oxygen transfer rate. *Xanthomonas spp.*, being aerobic suggests that with more dissolved oxygen, more xanthan gum will be produced (Casas *et al.*, 2000; Papagianni *et al.*, 2001). However, higher dissolved oxygen commands for high aeration speeds, which prompts hydrodynamic stress and cell damage

thus negatively affecting the gum yields (García-Ochoa *et al.*, 1997). Neutral pH is ideal for the growth of *X. campestris*. Lopes *et al.* (2015) established that pH values between 6 and 7 at 25-27 °C and pH level of 8.0 at 30 °C recorded better xanthan gum production with good viscosity. Other studies emphasizing the use of alkali include Sidkey *et al.* (2020); Luvielmo *et al.* (2016) and Shiram *et al.* (2021).

With Xanthan gum, the production is a result of fermentation that utilises *Xanthomonas spp.* and carbon rich/sugar rich substrates (Liberty *et al.*, 2019). Substrates can range from pure substrates to agro waste (Lopes *et al.*, 2015). Glucose is the common and ideal substrate for xanthan gum production in terms of the product yield, supply, and product quality (Salah *et al.*, 2011). However, this has been seen as unsustainable due to the increasing cost of glucose (Shiram *et al.*, 2021).

There has been exploration focusing on the utilisation of alternative carbon sources such as processing residuals and agro waste. Alternative substrates include starch, hydrolysed starch, corn syrup, hydrolysed rice, barley and corn flour, acid whey, sugarcane molasses, coconut juice, sugar cane juice, beet molasses, date juice palm, and corn steep liquor (Abd El-Salam *et al.*, 1994; Gilani *et al.*, 2011; Naik *et al.*, 2023). Agro-industrial residues such as cassava bagasse and sugarcane bagasse, are other valuable alternatives. The choice of a substrate depends on factors such as availability, costs, and the expected characteristics of yield. Sugarcane juice or molasses is an ideal raw material because it has a high concentration of sucrose, mineral salts and vitamins, which gives it an outstanding nutritional value for xanthan gum production (Faria, *et al.*, 2011). Cassava bagasse contains 30–50 % starch on dry weight basis and has low ash content, while sugarcane bagasse is of abundant availability both being ideal for xanthan production (Agrawal, *et al.*, 2023; Thuppahige, *et al.*, 2023). However, sugarcane bagasse is utilized in the country for energy generation purposes (Omari *et al.*, 2020) while processing of cassava is still at a low level to generate the cassava bagasse at a rate capable of sustaining an industry.

Utilisation of agro-waste as the substrate of choice has been explored by several researchers including, potato peels (Vidhyalakshmi *et al.*, 2012), pineapple waste (Rashidi *et al.*, 2024), cheese whey and passion fruit peel (Santos *et al.*, 2021) and corncob (Jesus *et al.*, 2023) among others. There have also been studies on the utilisation of rice husks (Ozidal *et al.*, 2018; Jesus *et al.*, 2023) on their potential as a carbon source for xanthan gum production. The combination of the limited eco-friendly disposal methods of rice husks and its classification as a lignocellulose waste enhances its suitability as a potential carbon source for xanthan production. It is also economical and abundant given the quantity of rice produced annually across the globe.

In Tanzania, rice husks as a potential source are ideal as it avoids any usage conflict as seen with sugarcane bagasse. Rice husks are of abundant quantities unlike cassava bagasse and are currently not utilised or disposed of in a sustainable manner. The husks

are used for poultry farming, composting and burning to produce thermal and electrical energy (Moraes *et al.*, 2014). Rough rice production goes to about 3M tons per annum in Tanzania (IPAD, 2024). For every kilogram of rough rice, 0.28 Kg of husks are produced (Rice knowledge bank, 2016; Nguyen Van-Hung *et al.*, 2017). Rice husks are the hard outer layer of rice grains, separated during the milling process as a by-product. Rice husks are abundant among agricultural wastes as a by-product and essentially low cost (Laftah *et al.*, 2021). By composition, rice husks have 41.92 % carbon, 6.34 % hydrogen, 1.85 % nitrogen, 0.47 % Sulphur (Biswas *et al.*, 2017; Chakroborty *et al.*, 2023) and three polymers: cellulose 32-47 %, hemicellulose 19-27 %, and lignin 5-24 %. (Ngo *et al.*, 2022). Cellulose and hemicellulose can be broken down into fermentable sugars, which means that rice husks can be used as a substrate for xanthan production.

The production statistics and composition of rice husk suggests its potential as a raw material for xanthan gum industries, also presenting itself as an environmentally suitable waste management opportunity. However, before fermentation, rice husks should undergo hydrolysis treatment with hydrochloric acid and heating, as the yield from rice husks increases with longer heating times during hydrolysis (Pedroso *et al.*, 2019). A study conducted by Obidah *et al.* (2017) demonstrated a yield of 1.2 g/100ml of xanthan gum from rice husk flour.

Utilization of fermentation in Tanzania is not a novel process. It is used in a wide range of industries from the dairy sector to the brewery industry. The utilisation of bioreactors and fermenters for both batch and continuous industrial processing has been utilised in Tanzania although in other fields such as biogas production (Mshadente *et al.*, 2008), bioethanol production (Moshi *et al.*, 2015; Hamadi *et al.*, 2014), agro-waste conversion (Kivaisi *et al.*, 2010) and therefore not a novel technology. There is potential of combining the alternative source, rice husk, and the technology to produce xanthan gum.

Starch

The process used to produce starch is on a similar standing as Xanthan gum, that is, it is not a novel process to the country. In addition, starch production has attained the level of industrial production in the country, unlike the other agents. However, these factories have encountered issues such as limited raw material, quality control and market availability (personal communication).

Commercial extraction methods vary according to the source of starch. However, they can be grouped into traditional, mechanical or chemical extraction techniques. Under traditional extraction technique, one may have dry extraction and wet extraction. With dry extraction, the steps include the plant material being cleaned, dried, milled and sifted (Fonmboh *et al.*, 2020). A generalized view of wet extraction involves the cleaning of the plant source, processing into a starch slurry that is left to settle, the supernatant discarded, leaving a wet starch filtrate. The filtrate is dried in the sun and ground into a fine powder (Dorantes-Fuertes *et al.*, 2024).

Ghosal and Kaur (2023) explored this method looking at isolating starch granules from plant tissues, primarily from sources such as corn, potatoes, and wheat. The process starts with the pulverization of the plant material, followed by steeping in water to ensure that the tissue is soft and release the starch granules. The mixture is then centrifuged to separate the starch from plant fibres and proteins. This slurry is further washed and dried to obtain pure starch. Da Silva *et al.* (2020) also used a wet extraction process to extract the starch from three pigmented rice varieties.

Enzymatic methods or chemical methods of extraction involve the use of solvents and enzymes. With the solvent-based extraction, the process involves the processing of plant materials that includes suspension in solvents such as sodium hydroxide or ammonia for starch extraction (Li *et al.*, 2022). Enzymatic starch extraction involves using enzymes such as pectinase and cellulose to improve the starch extraction yield (Sit *et al.*, 2015).

Extraction by traditional wet milling enable starch purity up to 99.5 %, while enzymatic methods preserve higher structural integrity, which is important for pharmaceutical applications. With dry extraction, the quality of the starch is poor (Li *et al.*, 2022). Wet extraction is key for this paper as the output is for use in the food industry (Fig 2).

Conditions that impact starch production includes pH, water availability and quantity.

Figure 2: Industrial production process of starch (Source: Author's own, based on Ghosal and Kaur (2023))

Given that it is referred to as wet extraction, water plays a significant role. It is used to clean the raw material prior to processing, while during processing it aids in the extraction and distillation steps. Research by Hernandez-Carmona *et al.* (2017) for plantains and bananas, (Dorantes-Fuertes *et al.*, 2024) on tubers and roots and Rashwan *et al.*, (2024)

for different plants including rice further supported this explanation. pH levels of the process are important due to its impact on structural and quality properties of starch. Alkaline based extraction increases the production and recovery of starch due to facilitation of the reaction (Usman *et al.*, 2014).

A by-product of industrial processing, starch has been produced from a myriad of plants, such as cassava, rice, maize, potato among others. Sinkko *et al.* (2019) reported that conventional sources of starch are cereal and tubers. However, there have been efforts to explore alternative sources of starch such as fruit wastes including pineapple, mango, avocado, apple, and banana (Kringel *et al.*, 2020; Lan *et al.*, 2024; Tesfaye *et al.*, 2021; Bangar *et al.*, 2021). This increased interest in alternative starch sources is due to increasing market demand, industrial demand for new starches with different physicochemical, structural, and functional properties than conventional starch sources and the required food supply to meet the increase of world population (Scott *et al.*, 2020).

Pearl millet was selected as a potential source as it can be used in the current industrial process of wet extraction. It is also an underutilized crop with nutritional potential which needs to be utilized fully (Krishnan and Meera, 2018). It is a climate-resistant crop which may contribute to the income as well as food security of farming communities in arid and semi-arid regions (Srinivas *et al.*, 2022).

Pearl millet is a sustainable and favored starch source, constituting up to 70 % starch in its grain (Shobhit, 2020) and could be used as a cheaper source of starch as compared to other cereals for developing functional foods (Punia *et al.*, 2021). Characteristics that increase its potential include gelatinization, pasting properties, solubility, swelling power, and digestibility to infer wider application of the pearl millet starch (Punia *et al.*, 2021).

For Tanzania, pearl millet is of choice because in addition to being a climate resistant crop, increasing the marketing opportunities of the crop is seen as one of the ways to strengthen the value chain and ensure income generation for the stakeholders (Charles, 2013). Marketing of pearl millet products is hampered by lack of industrial interest, policy challenges and low consumer demand. While statistics on pearl millet production is limited (Rohrbach and Kiriwaggulu, 2001) hampered by other factors including lack of differentiation between pearl millet and millets of different species (Charles, 2013), available data indicate that the country produces at least 200,000 tons annually (Mwatawala and Nyabiri, 2021).

Utilization of pearl millet in starch production will ensure that the farmers will have an alternative to the “subsistence crop trap¹” as termed by (Gupta *et al.*, 2017) and potentially create support in the form of policy and increased awareness of the benefits of the crop.

¹ According to Coomes *et al.*, (20110 “A subsistence crop trap arises when land poor households are limited to cropping only subsistence-oriented annual crops (e.g., manioc), and cannot extend the cropping phase to include longer maturing perennial cash crops”.

Guar

While pearl millet is cultivated in low quantities due to limited market, the next plant guar is still a novel crop in Tanzania, however, it can be grown in the same regions as pearl millet. This will increase income for the farmers and with an additive industry, create employment for the different regions. The study assessed the climatic and soil requirements essential for successful guar cultivation.

Guar plants thrive in warm, semi-arid to arid climates. They require temperatures ranging from 25° C to 35 °C during the growing season and are adapted to regions with low annual rainfall typically 400-600 mm (Gresta *et al.*, 2013). Regions like Dodoma, Singida, and parts of Manyara in Tanzania possess similar climatic conditions suitable for guar cultivation. Guar plants prefer well-drained sandy loam or sandy soil with a pH ranging from neutral to slightly alkaline pH 7.0-8.5, (Gresta *et al.*, 2013). These soil types are prevalent in the identified regions, making them suitable for guar cultivation.

Guar production also involves a form of extraction, a mechanical process that involves roasting of seeds, differential attrition, sieving and polishing (Mudgil, 2014). Seeds are broken and two halves of the endosperm are obtained. Fine fibrous husk separated from the unhusked guar split, resulting in refined guar splits which follow the process outlined in Figure 3 until the final product of guar gum.

Like in starch production, temperature and pH are important for guar production. During the production process sequence, the rate of hydration and achieving maximum viscosity is important and affected by the temperature range. High temperatures of 80 °C enable the achievement of maximum viscosity however prolonged exposure leads to degradation (Nur and Yagoub, 2013). Guar gum solutions prepared at low temperature over a long period have a higher final viscosity than those prepared through application of heat. Studies have indicated that ideal temperatures range is between 25°- 40°c (Srichamroen, 2007). The increase in viscosity of guar gum solution is directly proportional to the guar gum concentration. While temperature and concentration are main factors, pH of guar gum is stable within the scale of 1.0-10.5 due to its non-ionic and uncharged behaviour (Mudgil *et al.*, 2014). However, hydration occurs faster in pH levels of 8-9 while it is slowest at pH levels above 10 and below 4.

Guar gum industrial process incorporates different techniques that are commonly used in Tanzania; milling (used in the cereals and grains processing), filtration and alcoholic precipitation (various liquid based industries). The need therefore is focused on ensuring the process is adapted for guar gum production while guar cultivation will increase income streams.

Agar

Figure 3: Industrial manufacturing process for guar gum (source: Author's own based on Chowdhary, 2002)

Agar production relies on a form of extraction utilising known techniques. Among the different techniques (Figure 4) syneresis is a key method. Within industries, agar is produced mainly through the syneresis method (Pandya *et al.*, 2022) as it is less costly and ensures the removal of soluble contaminants at a comparatively higher rate. The freeze-thaw method has been identified to be costly due to the high energy requirement (Padmesh *et al.*, 2021; Ayyakkalai *et al.*, 2024) and as such syneresis is seen as an ideal option for the industrial scale production of agar (Reddy, *et al.*, 2018).

Syneresis is the separation of liquid from a gel and can occur naturally especially in food products, however in the case of agar production, it is aided by the utilization of pressure applied through metal plates. Syneresis method employs the gelling quality of colloids, which allows absorbed water to be detached with the application of a sufficient force (Padmesh *et al.*, 2021). Syneresis follows the conventional method of extraction, however at the gelation stage (and following the bleaching stage), water is removed using pressure. The seaweed extracts were packed in cloths and crushed beneath stone blocks

(Pandya *et al.*, 2022) to aid the removal of water. After the process, the agar is shredded and dried before being milled.

Figure 4 outlines the process where the seaweed is heated with water and resultant solution filtered. Filtrate is left to cool and can be washed or treated with bleach depending on the properties of agar being sought. The gel is dehydrated either through freeze-thaw method or application of pressure, followed by a drying session in hot-air oven. The dried product is milled into uniform particles size (McHugh, 2003; Kaliaperumal and Uthirasiran, 2001).

During the production process, conditions that must be optimized include the extraction

Figure 4: Industrial production process for agar (Source: Author's own based on Pandya *et al.*, 2022; Jönsson *et al.*, 2020)

time, temperature, alkali concentration (Jönsson *et al.*, 2020; Villanueva *et al.*, 2010) and the pressure applied (Pandya *et al.*, 2022). There is also a need for constant reliable freshwater supply for agar production (McHugh 2003; Jönsson *et al.*, 2020).

Agar is typically extracted through solubilization in hot water (Jönsson *et al.*, 2020). As the process has been refined through the years, the most common way to extract agar is by boiling the seaweed in hot water, filtering it off and then separating the polysaccharide by a freezing and thawing cycle to eliminate water (Pandya *et al.*, 2022; Ayyakkalai *et al.*, 2024).

Research is ongoing with efforts in ensuring the industrial process is sustainable. There are some disadvantages such as ensuring the machinery used will lead to maximum extraction, necessitating the specialization of machinery (Reddy *et al.*, 2018). These efforts include the development of a process referred to the agar photobleaching process

(Pandya *et al.*, 2022). The cooking oil industry in Tanzania utilises a pressure-based method in acquiring their product. As such capacity to introduce syneresis is present in the country.

Similar to guar is the agar producing seaweed species. Tanzania is endowed with a rich biodiversity of seaweed species that grow naturally in its oligotrophic waters of the Western Indian Ocean. Commercial cultivation of seaweed is predominantly in the islands such as Zanzibar and Mafia as well as certain regions of the mainland's coast such as Bagamoyo and Tanga among others. Currently, the species cultivated in large quantities are *Eucheuma* and *Kappaphycus* (Kivaisi and Buriyo, 2005; Hayashi *et al.*, 2017; Msuya, 2010; Ward *et al.*, 2022) which can be processed to obtain carrageenan. However, research into the expansion of seaweed farming has identified red seaweed, *Gracilaria*, green *Ulva*, the red *Hypnea* and the brown *Sargassum* as potential species for farming (Msuya, 2020).

The presence of *Gracilaria* in the natural seaweed stocks indicates potential for the country to develop an industry and market for it. Studies have been conducted on the quality of agar that is extracted from the available *Gracilaria* stocks (Vuai, 2022; Vuai and Mpatani, 2019; Buriyo and Kivaisi, 2003) indicating the potential of the plants in providing raw materials for the production of the additive.

On the technological front, Tanzania has the capacity and capability to establish industries that can process the agents with adaptations to the different methods. However, it is important to ensure that the availability of the raw material is constant and dependable.

4. POLICY ENVIRONMENT

For Tanzania, agriculture has been the backbone of the economy for many years and there are efforts to increase industrialization through agriculture (Gupta, 2020; Bangi *et al.*, 2014). In 2018, the official statistics of Tanzania indicated that agriculture has the highest percentage of employment (63 %) which was a drop from 66.9 % in 2014. However, industries had increased from 6.5 % in 2014 to 7.3 % (Mwinuka and Mwangoka, 2023). Strengthening the aquaculture sector is also a key priority for the government for developmental purposes (Mosha *et al.*, 2020; Rukanda *et al.*, 2019).

Development of an industrial additive production plant will contribute to the development of the Agri and Blue Economies and industrialization initiatives of the country. Additionally, on an individual level it can increase the income generated for farmers. For the value chains, providing a domestic raw material source for the local food industries, and improvement of technologies for the associated value chains.

The regulations and policies that govern the additive industry in Tanzania mainly focus on the safety aspect of the additives. The Tanzania Bureau of Standards has a standard that outlines the permissible additives and their limits in different food products, TZS 115:1999. The selected agents are easily located within the list between

serial numbers 140-160. Another standard concerns the labelling of the additives, TZS 116:2020.

Using the potential sources of raw material as a guide, the study assessed relevant policies to identify the environment into which the proposed industry would function in as well as the standards that the resulting products must meet.

4.1 Agriculture policy 2013

All the identified raw material sources, except for seaweed, are products of the agriculture sector. The Agriculture policy of 2013 looks at achieving a sector that utilises natural resources sustainably as well as increasing the production of competitive crop products. The assessed food additives are part of a lucrative industry that is projected to grow as the years go by. As such they fall under the mission of the Agriculture policy of increasing the production of crop products.

Another objective of the policy is the increased production of crops according to the agro-ecological zones to enhance food security. This is through promotion of crop production and processing within the different zones. Pearl millet would greatly benefit from these activities as one of the shortcomings for its production is the lack of support in production techniques and marketing. Guar is not a commonly cultivated crop in Tanzania, however, there are regions that can grow it optimally with support and lead to it being an important competitive crop for the nation.

Operating under this policy are different strategies such as the Agricultural Sector Development Programme, currently in Phase II, outlining interventions centred on increasing production of strategic crops (like rice) and traditional crops (sorghum, millet). Due to the importance of rice, there is an additional strategy, the Rice Development Strategy (2019-2030), that seeks to increase rice production in the country to a point where the nation is self-sufficient (approximately 4 million tonnes per ha) in meeting its demand. It also promotes investment in development of rice-based products and by-products indicating a high production rate for rice husks.

4.2 Blue Economy Policy (Zanzibar) and Fisheries and Aquaculture (2015) policies

For seaweed production, Tanzania is focused on increasing the production of the plant as well as developing the associated processing industries. Exportation of seaweed contributes approximately 11 % to Zanzibar's foreign earnings (Msuya, 2012). However, given that it is exported raw, the earnings are considerably lower than if the seaweed was processed domestically (REPOA, 2021). The Zanzibar policy places as one of its objectives, "strengthening the market for aquaculture products, emphasis on developing industrial potential for refined seaweed and other aquaculture products". Within the National Fisheries Policy (2015), one of the policy statements indicate the government's commitment to promoting the establishment of aquaculture processing plants in the country.

The current Fisheries Master Plan (2021-2036) outlines the potential of aquaculture for the nation, and outlines actions to be undertaken to improve the seaweed value chain from increasing access to inputs, equipping the farmers with technical skills and financial support as well as creating an environment that will foster commercial seaweed farming.

4.3 Zanzibar Industrial Policy (2019) and Integrated Industrial Strategy

Zanzibar's industrial Policy acknowledges the importance of establishing industries to add value to ocean products such as seaweed. (RGOZ, 2020). The Integrated Industrial Development Strategy-Tanzania (2025) emphasises the activation of the rural economy through agricultural development led industrialization, encompassing the entire value chain stating that agro-processing industries being located within the areas that the raw material is sourced will create job opportunities.

4.4 National Climate Strategy (2021-2026)

Among a range of interventions outlined in the climate strategy, interventions relevant for the study are three in number. These are: the promotion and production of drought tolerant crops, diversification of livelihoods among the coastal population, and the utilisation of solid waste efficiently. Small scale processing of seaweed is currently being implemented, generating employment opportunities for the local community, while as mentioned earlier, the increased production of pearl millet will ensure income for people. The utilisation of rice husks contributes to waste management.

Overall, establishment of an additive industry in the country will meet with policies that are geared towards ensuring the availability of raw materials. There is a need to establish quality standards for the resulting additives, although there are currently a few that concern food-grade cassava-based starch and maize based edible starch. The national drive to industrialization should essentially support such an endeavor.

5. DISCUSSION

The research question "Does Tanzania have the resources necessary to successfully establish a food additives industry?" was answered in that there are raw material sources in different forms and technology in use by other industries that can be adapted for food additive production.

5.1 Raw materials

The study focused on the identification and potential utilisation of resources that are underutilised in the country and can contribute to different initiatives in the country such as sustainable utilisation of waste (rice husks), the development of an industry (seaweed) or income generation through increased cultivation (pearl millet and guar).

Based on the identified resources, Tanzania has the capability to produce additives nationally. With the increased rice production and drive to increase value added products

through the National Rice strategy (2019-2030), there is abundant generation of rice husks and the utilization of these as a carbon source will contribute to ensuring the rice value chain is a zero-waste industry. Additionally, the production of xanthan gum nationally will ease the pressure on local small-scale processors in accessing the additive for their activities. It will also allow the nation to benefit from the xanthan gum market especially once an industrial scale operation is optimized and put into operation.

While guar cultivation is low in the country, it is important to note that production of a commercially viable crop is possible given the different regions that can support the cultivation of the plant. There is an opportunity for the country to establish a domestic sustainable value chain with guar at the centre that ensures a market for the cultivating farmers and creating an opportunity for processors, as the number of products obtained from processing guar are numerous.

The need for value added products is important as seen with the seaweed industry where the commercially viable produce is exported raw while the domestic market imports the processed products for use. Tanzania, specifically Zanzibar, are leading producers of seaweed and there is untapped potential for the stocks of *Gracilaria*. However, value addition activities are at a small scale and access to markets is limited. With opportunity for development of the seaweed value chain through ~~with~~ the Blue Economy strategy, supporting the development of agar processing industries will be beneficial.

Sources of starch vary from rice, potato and cassava among others. The paper focuses on pearl millet as a potential source due to the limited value addition products for this crop and limited consumption nationally. Assurance of a market for pearl millet will contribute to increased production and income for the stakeholders of the particular value chain.

Essentially, the identified raw materials for the food additives, with the exception of guar, are abundant within the national borders and currently have few value addition options being explored. With guar, the cultivation potential in terms of seeds and regions is abundant as well.

5.2 Adaptable technology

The current technologies mobilised for industrial production of the additives are not novel to the country. Industries ranging from energy production to sunflower oil utilise the systems or forms of the systems. There is a need to ensure that the technologies are adapted and optimised to produce the additives and ensure high-quality products are generated.

5.3 Importance to Tanzania

The establishment of an additive processing industry in Tanzania serves two purposes. The first is with regards to the growing food processing industry in the country. There are small, medium and large-scale industries that are constantly producing processed foods for the society. Currently, items such as additives are imported or left out of product formulations due to the cost implications. A domestic industry will increase access to these forms of processing aids and reduce production costs. Additionally, Tanzania can earn income on this industry through exports. The global market for additives is currently worth over USD 100 Billion and is projected to increase annually by at least 5 % (Grand View Research, 2024). This is a market that the additives industries can target.

The second purpose concerns the push for national industrialization; the establishment of such processing facilities will aid in achieving this goal and create employment opportunities for members of society. Under the different additives, it was noted that there is potential in Tanzania in terms of increasing the production of the different plants that act as the source of the additives as well as serving as an opportunity to strengthen the different value chains.

6. CHALLENGES

Despite the existence of resources to establish a food additive industry, there is also a need to ensure that there is support in the form of supportive policies, extension services with regards to modernized cultivation practices and utilisation of technology to maintain quality and overall awareness raising to ensure that stakeholders support the development of the value chain. Governmental support also in the form of entry into both the domestic and international markets is key for the success of the potential industry. There is also a need for research to ensure the optimization of the production process is achieved to ensure efficient production methods.

7. CONCLUSION

Nationally, the country has the resources and knowledge to develop an additives production industry based on texturizing agents. However, there is a need for support from research, extension services and the government to achieve this aim.

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